

The Stability Constants of Complexes of Cobalt(II) with N-Phenyl-o-Methoxybenzohydroxamic Acid

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Hydroxamic acids forms the metal complexes with a number of the metal ions. The N-Phenyl-o-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid (P-O-MBHA) complexes of some bivalent metal ions have been reported¹. In the present communication the Co(II) complexes of P-O-MBHA have been studied in 50% (v/v) dioxane water media. It is observed that the P-O-

Fig 1. Formation Curve for P-O-MBHA-Co(II) Complex.

MBHA-Co(II) complex does not follow the Irving Williams order $Mn < Co < Ni < Cu > Zn$. The cobalt (II) complexes have the higher stability than the nickel(II).

The metal ligand stability constants have been obtained from formation function curve, fig. 1. These have been calculated from \bar{n} , pR data, Table I, obtained by Calvin-Bjerrum^{2,3} titrations adopting the method of Irving and Rossotti⁴. The corrections in dioxane-water medium between the glass electrode reading, B, and stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration have been applied⁵.

TABLE I

N-Phenyl-o-methoxybenzo-Cobalt (II) Complex

B	5.00	5.50	6.00	6.50	6.70	7.25	7.50
\bar{n}	0.25	0.60	0.90	1.25	1.55	1.80	1.85
pR	8.10	7.63	7.17	6.70	6.57	6.02	5.78

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EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

The titrant, carbonate free potassium hydroxide was prepared by the method of Vogel⁶. The dioxane was purified⁷ and due allowance was made in mixing it with water⁸.

A Radiometer pH meter Model PHM 4c equipped with a calomel and glass electrode was employed for pH measurements.

Stability Constants : Into (thermostated at 35°) a three necked titration cell which accommodated a glass electrode, a limb of salt bridge to make the contact with calomel electrode a burette and an inlet of nitrogen, the following sets of solution were added.

(I) 0.01M HClO₄ and 0.0100M P-O-MBHA in 50% dioxane (by volume)

(II) 0.01M HClO₄, 0.0100M P-O-MBHA and 0.001M Co(ClO₄)₂ in 50% dioxane (by volume).

The solution was titrated with 0.1M KOH which was also prepared in 50% dioxane by volume.

The formation curve, representing \bar{n} , as a function of pR ($= -\log R$) of Co(II) complex with P-O-MBHA is reproduced in fig. 1.

The titration data on Co(II) complexes are given in Table 1, and metal ligand stability constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Thermodynamic Stability Constants of N-Phenyl-o-methoxybenzo-hydroxamic acid Metal (II) complexes at 35°

$$pK_a = 11.03^{14}$$

Metal	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log K ₁ K ₂	Ref.
Cu ²⁺	10.35	8.68	19.03	1
Zn ²⁺	8.63	6.65	15.28	1
Co ²⁺	7.96	6.60	14.56	This study.
Ni ²⁺	7.77	5.68	13.45	1
Mn ²⁺	6.80	5.67	12.47	1

The stability constants (Table 2) of P-O-MBHA follow the Irving Williams order⁹ Mn²⁺ < Ni²⁺ < Cu²⁺ > Zn²⁺ except the Co²⁺ complexes, which do not follow the order Mn²⁺ < Co²⁺ < Ni²⁺ < Cu²⁺ > Zn²⁺. The higher stability of Co(II) than Ni(II) was observed and the same order is obtained with benzohydroxamic acid complexes¹⁰. However, the Co > Ni was also reported for the other ligands viz., 4-nitro-2-aminophenol¹¹ and 8-hydroxy-2-methyl-quinolinol^{12 13}.

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